

Hòa Hảo

also known as “Phật Giáo Hòa Hảo”, “Hòa Hảo Buddhism”

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Entry tags: Vietnamese Religions, Religious Group, Viet-Muong, Austroasiatic, Language, Vietnamese, Phật Giáo Hòa Hảo, PGHH, Bửu Sơn Kỳ Hương, Vietic

Hòa Hảo is a Vietnamese Buddhist religious movement that was founded in 1939 by Pontiff Huỳnh Phú Sổ (Huỳnh Phú Sổ) in Hòa Hảo village, Tân Châu district, Châu Đốc province (current name: Phú Mỹ town, Phú Tân district, An Giang Province). Hòa Hảo Buddhism was also one of the millenarian sectarian movements in southern Vietnam in 19th and 20th centuries. Born into a wealthy family as a fragile boy, Huỳnh Phú Sổ often needed medical assistance from different healers in the Mekong Delta region, and especially those from the sacred mountains of Thất Sơn (Seven Mountains). After a bodily collapse, he claimed himself to be the reincarnation of Đức Phật Tây An (the Buddha Master of Western Peace). The Buddha Master's real name was Đoàn Minh Huyền, who founded Bửu Sơn Kỳ Hương religion (Strange Fragrance from the Precious Mountain) in mid-19th century. Huỳnh Phú Sổ gained popularity and attracted followers by the same methods of Đoàn Minh Huyền: predicting apocalyptic events, preaching religious philosophy, and healing a large number of people. Huỳnh Phú Sổ had written Hòa Hảo Buddhist scriptures in verses and in literature texts (Sấm Giảng) during 1939-1947 before disappeared in an unclarified event. The circumstance around his death was contested, but his disappearance gave rise to debates about his alleged position towards Vietnamese Communist Forces (Việt Minh). The event took place in the power struggle context of southern Vietnam: imperialism, millenarian, colonization, nationalism, and later, the southern Buddhist Reform in 1930 (Chấn Hưng Phật Giáo). Caught in a conflicting position with different regimes, Hòa Hảo Buddhism has redefined and renewed its political and religious positions since 1937. The current Vietnamese government acknowledged Hòa Hảo Buddhism as a state-recognized religious group in 1999. Even though there are many different Hòa Hảo groups, The Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism (Ban Trị Sự Trung Ương Phật Giáo Hòa Hảo) is the only recognized group who has headquarter in An Hòa Tự Temple in Phú Mỹ town, Phú Tân district, An Giang Province. The Central Executive Committee has rewritten the scriptures and pushed forward a social identity based on charity and volunteerism. Hòa Hảo Buddhism is currently one of the most influential religions in the Mekong Delta.

Date Range: 1937 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Executive committees of Giáo hội Phật giáo Hòa Hảo

Region tags: Southern Vietnam, Vietnam, Central Vietnam, Cà Mau, Bình Định

Through 2012, the Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism had set up 369 communal executive committees from Southern to Central Vietnam (from Cà Mau to Bình Định Province). There are also organizations for Hòa Hảo that have been established in Houston, Texas and Atlanta, Georgia in the United States.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: <https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674433700>

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.phatgiaohoahao.org.vn/>

– Source 1 Description: Website of the Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Diverting from Bửu Hương Kỳ Sơn Tradition, Hòa Hảo Buddhism shares similarity and distinction with other indigenous religions such as Cao Đài, Tứ Ân Hiếu Nghĩa, Hiếu Nghĩa Tà Lơn, and Tịnh độ Cư sỹ Phật hội Việt Nam. In Vietnamese modern history, these new religions in the south have all competed for power and influence.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Bửu Sơn Kỳ Hương and later Hòa Hảo Buddhism have their religious philosophy and foundation based on Buddhism, Confucian, and Vietnamese folk religions.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Hòa Hảo Buddhists go to refuge by reading a text (Bài Quy Y) in the Prophetic teachings (Sấm Giảng), which was composed by Master Huỳnh Phú Sổ.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: New participants need assistance and recommendation of two Hòa Hảo Buddhists. Reading loudly a poem in the scriptures (Bài Quy Y) is an important participation practice/ritual that the new participant has to do in front of Hòa Hảo's sacred space (home altars or in temples).

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: In the period 1939-1975, during the First and the Second Indochina War, Hòa Hảo Buddhism had had some support from different regimes and political parties. In the period 1975-1999, Hòa Hảo Buddhists' religious practices and social gatherings had been strictly supervised and outlawed. Hòa Hảo religious leaders have been seeking support from the Communist Party since the religion was

officially recognized as a religion by the Vietnamese State,

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1939 CE - 2024 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1300000

Notes: In 1999, the Vietnamese State recognized Hòa Hảo Buddhism as a religion. The Vietnam Government Committee for Religious Affairs (GCRA) announced in 2010 that Hòa Hảo Buddhism had about 1,3 millions followers. A Vice Head of Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism claimed that the religion had many more followers nowadays, and in 1999, Hòa Hảo Buddhism had about two millions followers (personal interview in 2023). Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism also train and certify Hòa Hảo priests, who do not become monastic.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1999 CE - 2024 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: Hòa Hảo religion is categorized as a Buddhist minority sect in Southern and Central Vietnam, in comparison to the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS) (Giáo Hội Phật Giáo Việt Nam).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1999 CE - 2024 CE

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

A single leader of a local community:

– Field doesn't know

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

Notes: The Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism oversees communal Executive Committees. In cities, Hòa Hảo Buddhists may get assistance from the Central Committee (in sending recommendation to provincial Vietnam Fatherland Front) in order to establish a Representative Committee.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

Notes: Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ claimed to be the reincarnation of the Buddha Master of Western Peace (Đức Phật Thầy Tây An), who possessed healing power.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: The Central Executive Committee has a five year term. Members of the Committee vote for their leader positions in a General Meeting, which is organized at the sacred temple An Hòa Tự in Phú Tân in the end of each term.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1999 CE - 2024 CE

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures of Hòa Hảo Buddhism were written by Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ during 1939-1947, providing Buddhist teachings in Vietnamese (chữ quốc ngữ) and in simplified language. These canonical texts were divided into two parts (by the Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism). The main part is Prophetic teachings (Sấm Giảng), which has 6 parts: 1) Prophetic Teachings-Exhorting a Pious Life (Sấm giảng khuyên người đời tu niệm) (published in 1962 by Thương Bình Publisher in Sai Gon) 2) Thunder lectures of Hòa Hảo Buddhism (Sấm Giảng) (wrote by Huỳnh Phú Sổ in 1939 in Hòa Hảo Village) 3) Litanies of a Mad Monk (Kệ dân của người khùng) 4) Teachings on the non-Action of the Spirit (Giác mê tâm kệ) (wrote by Huỳnh Phú Sổ in 1939) 5) Encourage Good (Khuyến thiện) (wrote by Huỳnh Phú Sổ in 1941) 6) Guilines for the Practices of Religion of Partriarch Huynh (Cách tu hiền và sự ăn ở của người bổn đạo) (wrote by Huỳnh Phú Sổ in 1945) The other part is Hòa Hảo Prophetic Sutras. It is a collection of 253 poems and literature texts written by the Prophet in the period 1939-1947.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The canonical texts of Hòa Hảo Buddhism have been verbally transmitted by followers and believed to have desired power.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures were written by the Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ based on his prediction of terrible disasters and on millenarian myth of the Dragon Flower Assembly (Hội Long Hoa). Vo Duy Thanh summarized the apocalyptic myth: " The apocalyptic myth prophesised the appearance of the Future Buddha, Maitreya, also called the King of Light, or Minh Vương, who would be sitting on a lotus throne to convene the Dragon Flower Assembly, where only morally pure people who had survived the apocalypse would gather. The Thất Sơn (Seven Mountains)

was the place where the Future Buddha would descend after the world had been purified after the apocalypse. By Huỳnh Phú Sổ's time, it was believed, 'the Low Era was coming to an end, and the Dragon Flower Assembly was about to be opened' (PGHH 1965:71). The Low Era, or Hạ Ngươn, was believed by Hoà Hảo adepts to be nearing its end and would be replaced by yet another High Era, or Thượng Ngươn, a Golden Age, after the predicted cataclysm" (2022, p. 42).

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures were inspired by mystical practices of the Living Buddha Master of Western Peace, who has been considered as a god/deity by many religious practitioners in the Mekong Delta.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1939 CE - 1947 CE

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The Sacred Mountains of Thất Sơn (Seven Mountain) was believed to be a supernatural space embedded with mythical power and creatures, which revealed magical and healing power to the Living Buddha Master of Western Peace, and later to Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: After several texts were written and published in 1939 by the Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ, many followers believed him to be a Living Buddha, who also possessed healing power. His followers referred to his low education background, which was insufficient to preach and cure people in mass. Therefore, he was an embodiment of divine human beings, such as the Living Buddha Master of Western Peace, who communicated with the mundane world through the Prophet's spoken words and written texts.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures are rich with Buddhist philosophical references and stories of national martyrs. The poems and literature texts also describe mythical practices of religious pioneers in the Mekong region.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: The current (acknowledged) scriptures have been modified and adjusted by the Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism to adapt to current Vietnamese political and religious contexts.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnam Government Committee for Religious Affairs (GCRA) guides interpretation of religious scriptures by recognized religious groups in Vietnam.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Hòa Hảo Buddhist priests receive training from the Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism to teach and transmit the scriptures.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1050000

Notes: The sacred buildings and statues of Hòa Hảo Buddhism are currently concentrated in Núi Cẩm(or Thiên Cẩm Sơn, one of the seven sacred mountains Thất Sơn), which is located in

An Hảo commune, Tịnh Biên town, An Giang Province. The building complex is about 1050 hectares including sacred temples, sacred statues of the Future Buddha Maitreya (Phật A Di Đà) and Guanyin (Quan Âm).

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 33.6

Notes: The Maitreya Statue in Núi Cấm is 33.6 meter high.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Tombs of the parents of Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ are located in Chu Văn An street, Phú Mỹ town, Phú Tân district. They are sacred places to many Hòa Hảo Buddhists, which are: - Mộ Đức Ông (Tomb of Prophet Huỳnh's father Huỳnh Công Bộ) - Mộ Đức Bà (Tomb of Prophet Huỳnh's mother)

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: The cemetery of Huỳnh family is one of the sacred places of Hòa Hảo Buddhism, which attracts many pilgrims each year. Located behind the ancestral hall to the Hoà Hảo founder (Tổ Đình), it hosts the tombs of Prophet Huỳnh's parents.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The sacred temple An Hòa Tự (Chùa Thầy) is located on street no. 954, Phú Mỹ Town, Phú Tân District, An Giang Province. This 16000 meter complex also host the head quarter of the Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism. The temple's architecture has been unchanged since the day the Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ used it to found Hòa Hảo Buddhism on

18th day of the 5th month of the Kỷ Mão lunar year 1939.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: There are three different altars in Hòa Hảo temples and at home of Hòa Hảo followers: are dedicated to three different altars 1) The Buddha's altar (Bàn Thờ Phật) - The altar is dedicated to the Triple Jewel (Tam Bảo) - Buddha, Dharma, and the Sangha; - It is positioned at the highest level. There is no Buddha statue but a piece of brown cloth (Trần Đà) and a portrait of Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ (which has to be positioned under the brown cloth). 2) The ancestral altar (Bàn Thờ Cửu Huyền Thất Tổ) - The altar is dedicated to practitioners' ancestors; - It is positioned under the Buddha's altar. 3) The heaven's altar (Bàn thờ Thông Thiên) - The altar enables communication between the Heaven and the Earth; - It is positioned outdoor, in front of the house.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: Hòa Hảo religious flag is rectangular in shape with no pictures or letters. The maroon brown flag is displaced in Hòa Hảo temples, in working places of Executive Committees, and in locations that followers gather in official days for organized festivals and pilgrimages.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism organizes mass gatherings and pilgrimages in Phú Tân in two occasions each year: 1) The anniversary of Hoà Hảo Buddhism's Inauguration Day (18 May) 2) The Anniversary of the prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ's Birthday (25 November) In these two occasions, religious followers are allowed to meet in mass not only in Phú Tân, but also in temples and locations marked with the Hòa Hảo Buddhist flags.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The brown cloth on the Buddha's altar symbolizes the identity of mind and Buddha (Phật tức tâm, tâm tức Phật)

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The symbol of the Hoa Hao Buddhism is a white lotus flower with four petals on a brown colored background, above which is the yellow inscription "Phật Giáo Hòa Hảo". The lotus and the inscription are encircled by a yellow circle.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Núi Cấm in the Seven Mountains is the sacred mountain of Hòa Hảo.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Hòa Hảo Buddhists often do pilgrimages every year to the sacred mountain Núi Cấm, An Hòa Tự temple, and Tổ Đình.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Non-dualistic nature of body and mind (Thân Tâm Nhất Như)

Notes: The one-ness of body and mind (Thân Tâm Nhất Như) is a spiritual goal for many Hòa Hảo Buddhists. It can be achieved by carrying out rituals and practices such as meditation.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: The Prophet Huỳnh Phú Sổ claimed himself to be the reincarnation of the Buddha Master of Western Peace.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: According to Hòa Hảo Buddhist's belief, a moribund corpse goes through a process in which karma of the death person and his/her relatives evaluated. The dying person and his adherents need to pray to the Buddha intensively until the moment of death (pháp môn niệm Phật). His/her family and relatives will assist the soul to Nirvana or a good rebirth realm by praying continuously afterwards (often 1-2days), making a custom called "Tử Thì Táng" among Hòa Hảo communities.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: "Tử thì táng"

Notes: According to Hòa Hảo Buddhist's belief, a moribund corpse goes through a process in which karma of the death person and his/her relatives evaluated. The dying person and his adherents need to pray to the Buddha intensively until the moment of death. His/her family and relatives will assist the soul to Nirvana or a good rebirth realm by praying continuously afterwards (often 1-2days), making a custom called "Tử Thì Táng" among Hòa Hảo communities.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Valuable items:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other grave goods:
– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– Yes

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:
– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The Prophet was believed to be a Living Buddha.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Living Buddha Master of Western Peace (and later his reincarnation - the Prophet) is believed to be a descendant of Tây Sơn Family in Quy Nhơn, Bình Định.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Ancestor connection

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The Prophet predicted that the world would be purified after an apocalypse and that the Future Buddha would appear on the Forbidden Mountain (Núi Cấm) to begin a Golden Age. Hòa Hảo Buddhists have to be morally pure to survive the apocalypse and live in the new Age.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Healing power

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: Healing Knowledge

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: The Prophet is believed to come back and continue to lead his followers to the Golden Age.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Sấu Năm Chèo is a mythical animal, who took the shape of a crocodile in Sấm Giảng (Hòa Hảo Buddhist scriptures).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: Carry sinful people to underwater worlds

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: Healing power

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– I don't know

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– Yes [specify]: Hòa Hảo pantheon is based on Buddhism, which, has a wide range and a high hierarchy of Bodhisattva, local guardians and deities.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Eightfold Noble Path guides Buddhists to a successful spiritual path.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: The religion has a canon with food and alcohol taboo

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Avoid killing and adhere to become vegetarian, at least 4 days in a month.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: To Hòa Hảo Buddhist, home is the one of the most important sacred spaces.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: On the Buddha's altar at home, a piece of brown cloth (Trần Dà) is dedicated to the Triple Jewel, and therefore, is sacred.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Buddhists have to cultivate themselves for good karma based on Eightfold Path (Bát Chánh Đạo).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: In order to avoid bad karma from speech, Buddhists have to cultivate pure speech and avoid four crimes related to speech: slandering (lưỡng thiệt), swindling (vọng ngữ), idle chattering (ỷ ngôn), rude speaking (ác khẩu).

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The Four Debts (Tứ Ân)

Notes: Debt to the nation, debt to parents and ancestors, debt to the Triple Jewel – Buddha, Buddhist teaching, and Sangha, and debt to fellow countrymen and mankind

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Based on karma.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhists practice self-cultivation and generate merits from good deeds (phước duyên)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Contemporary Hòa Hảo Buddhism emphasizes on charity and volunteerism as journeys for social activism, which may give reward in a form of individual and family prosperity.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Hòa Hảo Buddhist canon prohibits meat of water buffaloes and dogs.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

To other in-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Social engagement and volunteerism characterize Hòa Hảo Buddhism nowadays. In order to be a dedicated member of their community, Hòa Hảo Buddhists need to do volunteer works and participate in social gatherings, often at other Buddhists' home, where they carry out collective rituals.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 14

Notes: Home is sacred space. Hòa Hảo Buddhists adherents worship twice a day at home, though not strictly with regard to worship time. The worship time is often in the early morning from 4:00–6:00, and in the evening from 5:00–7:00. On the first and 15th of each lunar month and on Buddhist holy days, followers usually go to Hòa Hảo temples or community worship places to pray and listen to sermons.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimages are done each year to the religion's birthplace (Phú Tân) especially on 18.5, lunar calendar. It is the anniversary of Hoà Hảo Buddhism's Inauguration Day. Number of participants can

reach to more than one hundred thousands.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 30000

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Hòa Hảo priests (giáo lý viên) are trained by the Central Executive Committee. In order to preach, they have to pass exams and receive certificates from the Central Committee

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1999 CE - 2024 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Male Hòa Hảo Buddhists in several communities adhere to long hair, which is tied tidily to the back of their neck. Hair length may indicate that a member belong to a certain group.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: In order to differentiate from unrecognized religious groups by the State, the Central Executive Committee appoints a dress code for their priests. In an interview with a member of the Committee (April 2022), scrutiny activities of online sermons (based on the dress code) have been carried out.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Notes: The Prophet's father (Đức Ông) and younger sister (Huỳnh Thị Kim Biên) were believed to receive the Prophet's power after 1947.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Humanitarian works are emphasized by Hòa Hảo devotees. Before, during, and after the Covid-19 pandemic, Hòa Hảo Buddhists have set up many rice kitchens inside hospitals, near schools, and near local Red Cross locations, providing free meals to people in need.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Hòa Hảo had a university before 1975, specializing in Buddhist philosophy and Hòa Hảo scripture education. The university was abolished by the new government after the Second Indochina War. Currently, the Central Executive Committee of Hòa Hảo Buddhism has a new building in front of An Hòa Tự Temple ready for a college. Nevertheless, disputes in the teaching curriculum of Hòa Hảo's history has put off grand opening plan for the college in 2023.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to food, herbal medicine is stored in temples.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: Charitable bridges and road building activities are provided.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Funds are mobilized by Hòa Hảo Buddhism and the Vietnamese People's Committee at all levels.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

– Yes

Notes: Tithes are expected among dedicated members in a Hòa Hảo Buddhist community.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: In World War II, Hòa Hảo Buddhism had an army, which became a strong force at the end of the war. In the Second Indochina War, different Hoà Hảo army forces had assumed offensive throughout the Mekong Delta.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1937 CE - 1975 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Hòa Hảo's army forces was believed to collaborate with different army forces during 1939-1975.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1937 CE - 1975 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1939 CE - 1947 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1939 CE - 1975 CE

Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1939 CE - 1975 CE

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Notes: It was known to have different Hòa Hảo groups, who maintained full-time military corps during the First and the Second Indochina War. In particular, army forces under General Lâm Thành Nguyên, and General Nguyễn Giác Ngộ had strong hold in Long Xuyen.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1939 CE - 1975 CE

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1939 CE - 1975 CE

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Hòa Hảo scriptures were written in Vietnamese alphabet in 1930s-1940s, which were a new language system in the region. Written language in the Mekong Delta at the time was French, Khmer, Chinese, and chữ Nôm (the logographic writing system of the Vietnamese language). In order to differentiate from chữ Nôm, the Prophet Huynh wrote his teachings in the Vietnamese alphabet (Quốc ngữ).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1937 CE - 1947 CE

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Vegetarian meals are expected in 4 days each month (1, 14, 15, and one day before the first day of the lunar month), when Hòa Hảo Buddhist go to temples and listen to sermons.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Haseman, J. B.. "The Hoa Hao; A Half-century of Conflict" 3, no. 6 (1976): 373–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00927678.1976.10554207>.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Bourdeaux, P.. "Being Engaged in the World (nhập Thế) and the Secular State in 20th Century Vietnam. Approaching Two Notions Through Hòa Hảo Buddhism History". *Theory and Society* 51, no. 5 (June 30, 2022): 871–92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11186-022-09488-y>.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Vo, T. D.. "The Great Unity: Hòa Hảo Buddhist Charity and Social Solidarity in the Borderland" 17, no. 4 (2022): 18–54. <https://doi.org/10.1525/vs.2022.17.4.18>.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Taylor, P.. "Apocalypse Now? Hoa Hao Buddhism Emerging from the Shadows of War". *The Australian Journal of Anthropology* 12, no. 3 (December 2001): 339–54. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1835-9310.2001.tb00242.x>.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Tai, H. TH.. *Millenarianism and Peasant Politics in Vietnam*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1983. <https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674433700>.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Taylor, P., ed.. *Modernity and Re-enchantment*. Edited by P. Taylor. AS-Yusof Ishak Institute: ISEAS Publishing, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1355/9789812304568>.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Huỳnh, N. T., and H. L. Dương. "Huynh Phu So's Innate Capacity of Establishing Hao Hoa Buddhism in Southwest Region". *Thu Dau Mot University Journal of Science* 4, no. 3 (September 15, 2022): 157–67. <https://doi.org/10.37550/tdmu.ejs/2022.03.317>.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Bourdeaux, P.. "Notes on the First Document in French Recording the Appearance of a New Religious Sect at the Hoa Hao Village (15-3-1940)" 36, no. 6 (December 19, 2006). <https://doi.org/10.3125/rsr.v36i6.252>.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Huỳnh, P. S.. *Tôn Chỉ Hành Đạo Của Huỳnh Giáo Chủ*. Saigon: Thương Binh Publisher, 1968.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Huỳnh, P. S.. *Sấm Giảng Giáo Lý Phật Giáo Hòa Hảo*. Long Xuyên, 1939.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Nguyễn, V. H., and S. Dật. *Nhận Thức Phật Giáo Hòa Hảo*. Long Xuyên: Hương Sen Publisher, 1968.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Thanh Sĩ, and Vương Kim. *Để Hiểu Phật Giáo Hòa Hảo*, 1966.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Trần, M. V.. "Beneath the Japanese Umbrella: Vietnam's Hòa Hảo During and After the Pacific War". *Crossroads: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Southeast Asian Studies* 17, no. 1 (1993): 60–107.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Vo, T. D.. *Repaying the Debts, Remaking the World: Hoà Hảo Buddhist Charity as*

Vernacular Development in Vietnam's Mekong Delta. The Australian National University, 2020.

Reference: Hòa Hảo, Bourdeaux, P. "The Emergence of Hòa Hảo Buddhism Under the Dual Franco-japanese Administration". Waseda University, n.d..